

Electron Population Controlled Mercuration of Thioamines

K. BAG^a, N. K. DE^a, B. R. DE^a and C. SINHA^{*b}

^aDepartment of Chemistry and Chemical Technology, Vidyasagar University, Midnapore-721 102

^bDepartment of Chemistry, University of Burdwan, Burdwan-713 104

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The mercuration of thioanilines indicates the dimercuration per aryl ring. The position of the substitution is established by electron density calculation using MNDO method.

Metal directed activation of the C-H bonds in organic molecules that could lead to new functionalization at carbon centre is one of the attractive topics in current research^{1,2}. Several significant advances towards the realization of this objective using transition metal complexes have been reported³. Organo-nontransition compounds are relatively less familiar than transition cousin, may be due to their weak coordinating ability. Mercury is one of the nontransition elements whose organic chemistry has attracted a great attention^{2,4,5}. The mercuration of aromatics are electron population controlled^{5,6}. The stability of the products arises from the conformation of the substrate. In our earlier report we suggested the regioselective mercuration of thioazomethines⁵. Herein we give an account on the mercuration of *S*-alkylated 2-aminothiophenols, and the products are established by spectroscopic studies. The site of mercuration is supported from theoretical electron density calculation by modified neglect of differential overlap (MNDO) method.

Results and Discussion

Thioamines and mercured products are summarized in Scheme 1. Microanalytical data support dimercuration

(i) Na/EtOH, (ii) R-X, (iii) Hg(OAc)₂/McOH, LiCl, (iv) (CH₂)₂Br₂ or (CH₂)₃Br₂.

Scheme 1.

per aryl ring of the thioamines. The compounds are thermally stable and decompose above 400°. The ir spectra give two well-defined sharp medium intense stretch at 310–315 cm⁻¹ (HgCl)⁷. The amino group appears as ν_sNH 3375 and ν_{as}NH, 3480 cm⁻¹. The ν_{C-S} appears at 760–775

cm⁻¹ and ν_{S-CH} as split band⁸ at 660–680 and 640–650 cm⁻¹. Due to insolubility of the compounds in common organic solvents (benzene, acetonitrile, alcohols), the electronic spectra were recorded in DMSO. The spectra exhibit two transitions at 260–270 and 310–325 nm, ascribed due to intraligand charge transfer transitions.

The position of mercuration is difficult to assign. The theoretical electron density calculation by MNDO method in collaboration with ¹H nmr data suggest some insight into the position of mercury atom. The data are collected in Table 1. The broad signal at δ 5.4 ppm is due to NH₂ protons. The S-Me protons resonate at δ 2.29 (1) while S-CH₂-CH₃ (2) gives a quartet at δ 2.69 and a triplet at 1.14 for CH₂ and CH₃ respectively. In compound 3, the CH₂ group of -S-CH₂Ph resonates at δ 3.94 and downfield shifting is due to electron-withdrawing character of neighbouring Ph group. The methylenic -(S-CH₂-)₂ in 4 appears as triplet at δ 2.59 and in (5) -(S-CH₂-)₂CH₂ exhibit a triplet and multiplet at 2.86 and 1.76 respectively.

The aromatic region of the compounds (1-5) display two well-defined singlet corresponding to two protons. There are four aromatic protons in each phenyl ring (H_A, H_B, H_C, H_D) of the thioamines (I). Hence two protons are substituted by -HgCl group. There will be in principle six dimercured isomers, of them three (II-IV) will have two singlet protons. But the exact nature of isomers could not be defined simply by ¹H nmr spectra. The mercuration

analogous to other electrophilic substitution⁹ is electron population controlled and the stability of the product is conformationally determined^{5,6}.

The mercuration of other aromatics may help us to define the substitution centre. In pyridine the substitution is directed to the *meta* position by Hg(OAc)⁺. The MO calculation suggests that this is the highest electron population position¹⁰. The *N*-phenylpyrazine directs Hg(OAc)⁺ at C-4 position, that is of highest electron density¹¹. The

azophenols are mercurated at phenolic ring *ortho* to the phenolic OH group¹². It is of highest electron density position due to electron-releasing effect of OH group. Aniline is mercurated at *ortho* and *para* positions² to NH₂ group; those are directly influenced by electron-releasing ability of this group. In *N*-benzylideneanilines, the mercuration takes place at *ortho/para* to the *N*-phenyl ring because of the higher electron densities at those sites^{6,13}. In 2-(alkylthio)-*N*-benzylideneanilines the mercuration is directed to the *para* position of the *N*-phenyl ring, because of the electron population of the site and conformational stability of the product⁵. Thus the selection of site for mercuration at the aromatic ring has electron population basis.

The MNDO method has been employed to calculate the electron density from optimized geometry of the molecule. The molecules are planar and their bond parameters are within the experimental error. The electron densities of the aromatic carbon centres are listed in Table 1. The data reveal that the positions of B and C are of higher electron densities for 2-methylthioaniline. Thus the mercuration may be directed to B and C positions. Hence the dimercurated products will be of the type IV. The idea is extended to other *S*-alkylanilines for their mercuration processes. In 1,2-bis[2-(aminophenyl)thio]ethane, the calculation shows (Table 1) that A and C sites are of higher electron densities and hence Hg(OAc)⁺ should be directed to those sites (type II). Thus the tetramercurated products (4) will be available which is supported by elemental analysis and ir data. The idea extended to 1,3-bis[2-(aminophenyl)thio]propane to suggest the site of mercuration at the product 5. The electron density calculation of 2-(*S*-methyl)-*N*-benzylideneaniline (6) suggests that the highest electron density position is *para* to the *N*-phenyl ring and this will be the predicted site for mercuration. This is in practice and is supported by ¹H nmr data⁵.

TABLE I—NET ATOMIC CHARGES (IN *e* UNIT) CALCULATED BY MNDO METHOD

2-(Methylthio)-aniline ^a		1,2-Bis[2-(aminophenyl)-thio]ethane ^b		2-(<i>S</i> -Methyl)- <i>N</i> -benzylideneaniline ^c	
Atom no.	Net atomic charge	Atom no.	Net atomic charge	Atom no.	Net atomic charge
C-1	-0.2902	C-1(1')	-0.2580(-0.2683)	C-1	-0.1849
C-2	-0.0761	C-2(2')	-0.0156(-0.0165)	C-2	-0.0662
C-3	-0.0340	C-3(3')	-0.1627(-0.1688)	C-3	-0.0367
C-4	-0.0480	C-4(4')	-0.0458(-0.0361)	C-4	-0.0605
C-5	-0.0574	C-5(5')	-0.1507(-0.1573)	C-5	-0.0359
C-6	-0.0196	C-6(6')	-0.0411(-0.0415)	C-6	-0.0510
S-7	-0.0615	C-7(7')	-0.1724(-0.1578)	N-7	-0.2563
C-8	-0.0331	S-8(8')	-0.0559(0.0412)	C-8	0.1446
N-9	0.6714	N-9(9')	0.0694(0.0567)	C-9	-0.0920
				C-10	-0.0216
				C-11	-0.0765
				C-12	0.0060
				C-13	-0.0806
				C-14	-0.0327
				S-15	0.0843
				C-16	-0.0497

Experimental

The solvents (A.R. grade) were dried¹⁴. Hg(OAc)₂ was purchased from Lancaster, U.K. All other chemicals were of reagent grade and used as received. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 783 and 883 spectrometers, ¹H nmr (300 MHz) spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Bruker Ac(AF) FT NMR spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and electronic spectra on a Shimadzu UV-160 A spectrophotometer. Elemental analyses were performed on a Perkin-Elmer 240C analyzer. The alkylthioamines were prepared by reported procedure⁵. All the mercurated products were synthesized according to common procedure as given for 3. A solution of Hg(OAc)₂ (0.80 g, 2.51 mmol) in dry MeOH (25 ml) was added dropwise to a solution of 2-benzylthioaniline (0.25 g, 1.16 mmol) in the same solvent (10 ml). The mixture was stirred at 60° for 1 h and then allowed to cool to room temperature, LiCl.H₂O (0.3 g, 4.96 mmol) in MeOH added and the resulting thick mixture stirred for 20 min. The light yellow precipitate was washed with ether, dried under reduced pressure and crystallized from DMSO-MeOH mixture, yield 85%; yields of other complexes 75–90%. ¹H nmr data of the mercurated products : **1** : H_A, 7.30(s); H_D, 6.73(s); S-CH₃, 2.51 and NH₂, 5.28(br); **2** : H_A, 7.34(s); H_D, 6.73(s); S-CH₂, 2.69(q); CH₃, 1.14(t); NH₂, 5.38(br); **3** : H_A, 7.36(s); H_D, 6.76(s); S-CH₂, 3.94(s); C₆H₅, 7.25(m); NH₂, 5.43(br); **4** : H_B, 7.16(s); H_D, 6.76(s); S-CH₂, 2.59(t); NH₂, 5.18(br); **5** : H_B, 7.24(s); H_D, 6.79(s); S-CH₂, 2.86(t); CH₂, 1.76(m); NH₂, 5.23(br).

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